

Probable Implication, the Contrapositive, and Contingency Tables*

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ABSTRACT

In everyday life, the deductive logic of mathematical reasoning must be replaced by inductive logic, which usually derives uncertain conclusions from a body of observed facts. We examine this distinction using probabilities based on 2×2 contingency tables. Some anomalies are discussed, such as the difference between the empirical probability of the implication $A \Rightarrow B$ and that of the logically equivalent contrapositive implication $\text{not-}B \Rightarrow \text{not-}A$, although they are almost equal under near certainty. Other classical examples are also discussed quantitatively, such as modus ponens and transitivity of implication.

In *deductive* (mathematical) logic, the usual interpretation of implication (Kleene [K1, p. 138]) is: "The implication $A \supset B$ means the same as $\neg A \vee B$ [i. e., not-A or B] and is called *material implication*..." For brevity, we will write $\neg A$ as A' , and the logical *conjunction* $A \wedge B$ (i. e., A and B) as AB . In this notation, clearly.

$$(A \Rightarrow B) \text{ iff } A' \vee B \text{ iff not-}AB' \text{ iff } (B' \Rightarrow A'). \quad (1.1)$$

(Here, as throughout the paper, "iff" is a convenient shorthand for "if and only if.") The proof invokes De Morgan's laws: $(AB)' = A' \vee B'$ and $(A \vee B)' = A'B'$.

1. Introduction

This paper is intended to clarify some basic differences between the properties of *implication* in logic-based reasoning and in common sense reasoning. In general, mathematical reasoning is based on *deductive* logic, which uses implication to go from hypotheses to conclusions that are believed to be *certain*. In everyday life, this must be replaced by *inductive* logic, which usually derives *uncertain* conclusions from a body of observed facts. Hence the relation "A implies B" (in symbols, " $A \Rightarrow B$ " or more formally " $A \supset B$ ") is no longer certain, although it still plays a fundamental role. It is with the properties of "probable implication" in inductive (or empirical) logic that this essay is concerned. Such uncertain inference has attracted some interest in the field of artificial intelligence, particularly in automated reasoning [CF, Ch. XII].

Mathematical logicians ([K2, p. 9], [T, p. 31]) and many others seem uneasy about material implication because, as Kleene [K1, p. 138] says, "The holding of $A \supset B$ does not require a necessary connection of ideas between A and B." See also Tarski [T, p. 26], who distinguishes between material implication and the more restrictive "formal" implication, which he characterizes by: "the presence of a certain formal connection between antecedent and consequent is an indispensable condition of the meaningfulness and truth of the implication. The concept of formal implication is not, perhaps, quite clear."

The role of inductive reasoning in science is emphasized in Jeffreys' opening sentences [J, p. 1]: "The fundamental problem of scientific progress, and a fundamental one of everyday life, is that of learning from experience. Knowledge obtained in this way is partly merely description of what we have already observed, but part consists of making inferences from past experience. This part may be called generalization or induction. It is the most important part ..."

A good reason for this uneasiness is provided by a more critical consideration of *probabilities* of implications as in Eq. (1.1), which asserts the well-known principle [K2, p. 59] that "A implies B" is equivalent to its *contrapositive*: "not-B implies not-A." This consideration is suggested by Jeffreys [J, p. 1], who cites J. Clerk Maxwell: "They say that Understanding ought to work by the rules of right reason. These rules are, or ought to be, contained in Logic, but the actual science of logic is conversant at present only with things either certain, impossible, or entirely doubtful, none of which (fortunately) we have to reason on. Therefore the true logic for this world is the calculus of Probabilities, which takes account of the magnitude of the probability which is, or ought to be, in a reasonable man's mind." We will show below that the *probability* that "A implies B" is *not* equal to the probability that "not-B implies not-A."

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Mathematically, the algebra of probability is closely related to Boolean algebra, which may be regarded simply as an algebra of sets which satisfies our intuitive notion of union, intersection and complementation (e. g., the commutative, associative and distributive laws). From the standpoint of Boolean algebra, an event can be regarded as a subset of a set X of possible events, and the (objective) probability of an event belonging to a set A can be described abstractly, following Kolmogorov, as a real function $P(A): 2^X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ essentially such that $P(X) = 1$, and $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B)$ when A and B are disjoint, i. e., when $A \cap B = \emptyset$. (Roberts [R, Chap. 8] distinguishes between

objective and subjective probability; see also [L, Chaps. 1-2], for instance). A standard interpretation of $P(A)$ is given by the notion of the relative frequency [CR, Chap. 2 Supplement].

Because logically equivalent propositions should have equal probabilities [G2, p. 19], we now define the *probability of material implication* (cf. (1.1)) as

$$P_m(A \Rightarrow B) = P(A \vee B) = P((AB')') = 1 - P(AB'). \quad (1.2)$$

Since $(A')' = A$, it follows that

$$P_m(A \Rightarrow B) = P_m(B' \Rightarrow A') : \quad (1.3)$$

the probability that A materially implies B equals the probability that not- B materially implies not- A .

The probability of material implication is less useful in common sense reasoning than that of *empirical* implication. We define this *empirical probability* that A implies B ("if A then B ") as the *conditional probability* ([F, p. 115], [G1, p. 67]) of B given A :

$$P(A \Rightarrow B) \equiv P(AB)/P(A). \quad (1.4)$$

Our distinction between material and empirical implication seems related to Tarski's distinction between material and formal implication. Since $P(AB) = P(A) - P(AB')$ and $P(A) \leq 1$, clearly

$$P(A \Rightarrow B) \equiv P(AB)/P(A) = 1 - P(AB')/P(A) \leq 1 - P(AB') = P_m(A \Rightarrow B). \quad (1.5)$$

We formulate this as a

Lemma. $P(A \Rightarrow B) \leq P_m(A \Rightarrow B)$.

Indeed, it can be shown that

$$P_m(A \Rightarrow B) - P(A \Rightarrow B) \equiv P(A')P(A \Rightarrow B') \geq 0.$$

(The authors thank I. R. Goodman for pointing this out.) Then, since $P(A) + P(A') = 1$ and $P(A \Rightarrow B) + P(A \Rightarrow B') = 1$, the two probabilities are nearly equal when either A or $A \Rightarrow B$ (empirically) is almost certain. This inequality gives added substance to Tarski's comment [T, p. 26] that his concept of formal implication is "narrower" than that of material implication.

2. Contingency tables.

To clarify further the relation of empirical (or "conditional") implication to material implication, we next recall the basic statistical concept of a *contingency table*.

In general, a bivariate contingency table relates two partitions, $\{A_i\}$ and $\{B_j\}$, of the same finite class of objects or events. The table records the frequency f_{ij} of (events) in each intersection $A_i B_j$. It is thus a contingency or frequency *matrix*, $F = (f_{ij})$, of nonnegative integers. The relative frequencies f_{ij}/n , where $n = \sum f_{ij}$ is the sum of the elements of F , evidently constitute a *probability matrix* whose entries are nonnegative rational numbers with sum one.

In the *two-valued* logic of deductive mathematics, such a probability matrix $P = (p_{ij})$ is necessarily a *unit matrix* $E^{hk} = (e^{hk}_{ij})$ whose only nonzero entry is $e^{hk}_{hk} = 1$. For any such matrix E^{hk} , evidently $P_m(A_i \Rightarrow B_j) = 1$ iff $j = k$, otherwise

$P_m(A_i \Rightarrow B_j) = 0$. Moreover, $P(A_i \Rightarrow B_j)$ is undefined unless $i = k$, while in this case $P(A_i \Rightarrow B_j) = P_m(A_i \Rightarrow B_j)$.

We will concentrate our attention below on 2×2 contingency matrices and the associated probability matrices $P = \begin{pmatrix} p & q \\ r & s \end{pmatrix}$. In

this case, we can set $A_1 = A$, $A_2 = A'$ and correspondingly $B_1 = B$, $B_2 = B'$. In terms of these entries, the empirical probability defined by (1.4) is clearly

$$P(A \Rightarrow B) = p/(p+q). \quad (2.1)$$

(Evidently, this probability of *empirical implication* is undefined and meaningless when $P(A) = 0$, i. e., when A is never observed.) This is *not* equal to $s/(q+s)$, the empirical probability of the logically equivalent contrapositive, unless $q = 0$ or $p = s$, in contrast to material implication for which the probabilities of $A \Rightarrow B$ and $B' \Rightarrow A'$ are always equal (Eq. (1.3)).

One very famous 2×2 contingency matrix is the following.

Example 1. Consider the proposition that "inoculation gives immunity". In 1915, Greenwood and Yule tabulated findings in 818 cases in the following contingency table related to a cholera epidemic.

	Not attacked	Attacked
Inoculated	276	3
Not inoculated	473	66

In this example, one easily verifies that

$$P_m(A \Rightarrow B) = P(A \vee B) = 815/818 = 99.63\%$$

is equal to $P_m(B' \Rightarrow A')$. On the other hand, the empirical (or conditional) probability $P(A \Rightarrow B)$ of "If A , then B " is 98.92%. This clearly differs from the empirical probability of the contrapositive implication, $P(B' \Rightarrow A')$, which is 96.65%.

Another example showing that the empirical probabilities of an implication and its contrapositive are not in general the same is the following.

Example 2. Let A be the statement that the father of X was born 105 or more years ago, and let B be the statement that X 's father is dead. The implication $A \Rightarrow B$ is "almost" certainly true. The contrapositive implication $B' \Rightarrow A'$ is "The father of X is alive; therefore he was (almost surely) born less than 105 years ago."

The following contingency table provides a "guesstimate" of the actual frequencies.

	Dead	Living
Born \leq 1884	40 million	120
Born $>$ 1884	60 million	120 million

The empirical probabilities of the two implications differ from 1 (certainty) by $3 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and 10^{-6} , respectively, and so are not equal.

Since the empirical probabilities of $A \Rightarrow B$ and its contrapositive in each of the preceding examples differ by so little, the reader

may be left with a vague feeling of "So what?" The following example is more striking.

Example 3. Consider the selection of a card drawn at random from a deck of playing cards. Let A be the choice of a face card (Jack, Queen, King) and B the choice of an honor card (10, Jack, Queen, King, Ace). Then the (a priori) contingency table assumes the following form:

	Honor card	Not-honor
Face card	12	0
Not-face	8	32

The corresponding probability matrix $P = (1/13) \begin{pmatrix} 12 & 0 \\ 8 & 32 \end{pmatrix}$ gives the appropriate probabilities. Moreover, in general, by the law of large numbers, we know that if the joint property AB has been true in m of a large number n of exhaustive and mutually exclusive cases AB, AB', A'B, and A'B' made under the same conditions, one can be reasonably confident that $P(AB) = p$ is nearly m/n . That is, the *a priori* probabilities (arising in games of chance, for instance) and the *a posteriori* or statistical probabilities obtained from the empirical contingency tables are almost certainly very close for sufficiently large samples.

In Example 3, the probability of the empirical implication $A \Rightarrow B$ is zero, whereas $P(B \Rightarrow A) = 2/5$. The corresponding probability of *material* implication, in contrast, is, by Eq. (1.2), $P_m(B \Rightarrow A) = 1 - p = 10/13$. Even worse, since material implication preserves the probability of the contrapositive, we see that $P_m(A \Rightarrow B) = 10/13$ instead of the zero that common sense tells us it should be.

We note that even though common sense favors empirical over material implication, as in Example 3, empirical implication runs counter to the notion that equivalent propositions have equal probabilities. I. J. Good formulates this notion as an axiom [G2, p. 19]; see also [J, p. 17].

3. Discussion

We have seen that the empirical probabilities of implication $A \Rightarrow B$ and its contrapositive are not equal unless $q = 0$ or $p = s$. However, this contraposition is *almost* valid when $q \ll 1$ or $|p-s| \ll 1$ (i. e., when $A \Rightarrow B$ is nearly certain or when $P(A)$ and $P(B')$ are nearly equal, respectively), as we see from the following easily derived result.

Theorem 3.1. The conditional (empirical) probabilities of the implication $A \Rightarrow B$ and its contrapositive $B' \Rightarrow A'$ satisfy

$$P(A)[1 - P(A \Rightarrow B)] = P(B')[1 - P(B' \Rightarrow A')] \quad (3.1)$$

or, equivalently,

$$\frac{1 - P(A \Rightarrow B)}{1 - P(B' \Rightarrow A')} = \frac{P(B')}{P(A)} \quad (3.2)$$

Hence, if A almost certainly implies B empirically, so that the left-hand side (= q) of (3.1) is very small, then B' almost surely implies A' unless B' is very unlikely. Likewise, if $P(A)$ and $P(B')$ are nearly equal, so that the right-hand side of (3.2) is nearly one, then the two empirical probabilities are nearly equal.

On the other hand, when $P(B')$, but not $P(A)$, is small enough, the empirical probabilities of $A \Rightarrow B$ and its contrapositive may be very different, as is shown by the following probability matrices, ordered in terms of increasing $P(A \Rightarrow B)$:

$$P_1 = \begin{pmatrix} .80 & .06 \\ .10 & .04 \end{pmatrix}, \quad P_2 = \begin{pmatrix} .90 & .009 \\ .09 & .001 \end{pmatrix}, \quad P_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1-2\epsilon-\epsilon^2 & \epsilon \\ \epsilon & \epsilon^2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

How greatly $P(A \Rightarrow B)$ and $P(B' \Rightarrow A')$ can differ is shown in the table below. Indeed, the third matrix shows that for any $\epsilon > 0$, no matter how small, the probability of an empirical implication can exceed $1-2\epsilon$ while its contrapositive has a probability less than ϵ .

	P_1	P_2	P_3
$P(A \Rightarrow B)$.930	.990	$> 1-2\epsilon$
$P(B' \Rightarrow A')$.440	.100	$< \epsilon$

Probabilistic reasoning

The contrast between the "inductive" and "deductive" logic of implication is well illustrated by the (hypothetical) textbook example of a person observing the result of flipping a coin repeatedly. If the coin turns up heads every time, how many flips are needed to convince one that the coin has heads on both sides?

The following personal experience also illustrates probabilistic reasoning.

Example 4. As a boy, one of us wandered into a room at boarding school where four fellow students were playing bridge. Noticing that the dealer's partner had 11 hearts, including AKQJ, he asked "Who fixed the deck?" The dealer responded "How did you guess it?"

With preparation, this question could have been answered as follows. There are four suits of thirteen cards each and $\binom{52}{13}$

$= 52!/13!39! = (6.35) \cdot 10^{11}$ different hands that can be dealt in bridge, all equally probable. The number of hands having AKQJ in one suit, and all but two of the remaining cards in that same suit, is $4 \cdot \binom{7}{2} \cdot \binom{41}{2} = 118,080$. Hence the *probability* of being

dealt such a strong suit is $(1.86) \cdot 10^{-7}$. Moreover, the probability of getting an even stronger suit is still less. The probability that the dealer stacked the cards in order to have some fun seemed very much greater, and therefore this was the probable explanation.

In a recent newspaper article [P], the following example shows how counterintuitive probabilistic reasoning may be.

FOR example, it's often mentioned in stories on drug or AIDS testing that there is a high percentage of false positives. What does this mean? Phrasing the exposition neutrally so as to avoid any factual questions, I'll assume there is a test for cancer that is 98 percent accurate; if someone has cancer, the test will be positive 98 percent of the time, and if one doesn't have it, the test will be negative 98 percent of the time. (Some tests are more reliable, but many, in particular the Pap test for cervical cancer, are considerably less so.) Assume further that 0.5 percent — one out of 200 people — actually have cancer. Now, imagine that you've taken the test and that your doctor somberly informs you that you've tested positive. The question is: How depressed should you be? The surprising answer is that you should be cautiously optimistic.

The author then shows clearly how "only 20% of those with positive tests will have cancer." This can also be easily explained with the help of a 2x2 contingency table.

Suppose, however, that the 98% accuracy refers instead to the percentage of people with positive test results who have cancer, and similarly the percentage of negative results among those without cancer. This is bad news for the patient who tests positive, but the *good* news is that such a situation is impossible. The data may be represented by the following probability matrix, in which "A" represents a positive test result and "B" the incidence of cancer. The marginal probabilities are a and $1-a$ for A and A', respectively, and .005 and .995 for B and B', respectively.

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} .98a & .02a \\ .02(1-a) & .98(1-a) \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $.98a + .02(1-a) = .005$, which gives an impossibly negative value for a .

Implication vs. causality

It is important to recognize the limits of contingency tables and not to infer from them a cause-and-effect relation between the events A and B.

Example 5. Upon arriving at work on an overcast morning, an observer noticed that the headlights had been left on in some cars in the parking lot. As a good citizen wanting to turn the lights off, he found all those cars locked. The following contingency table may be representative:

	Doors locked	Unlocked
Lights on	3	0
Lights off	100	100

What can one conclude from this evidence? There is no direct causal relation between A (lights on) and B (doors locked). Then the most likely conclusion is simply that the observer *got to work late*; he had probably been preceded by other good Samaritans who had already turned off the lights of cars that were unlocked. Hence, even though A implied B (and $B \Rightarrow A'$) with certainty, both empirically and materially, A did not *cause* B.

4. Properties of probable implication

Probabilities of implication have many other interesting properties.

Modus ponens

One of the oldest principles involving implication, and implicit in the construction of rule-based expert system tools such as EXPERT and EMYCIN [W, p. 105], is modus ponens: if A is true and $A \Rightarrow B$, then B is true. In dealing with uncertainty, however, we have to qualify these statements slightly: If A is almost true, in the sense that $1-P(A) \ll 1$, and A almost implies B materially, then B is almost true. For, as observed in [N, p. 76], $P(B)$ is bounded as follows in terms of the probabilities of A and $A \Rightarrow B$:

$$P(AB) = P_m(A \Rightarrow B) + P(A) - 1 \leq P(B) \leq P_m(A \Rightarrow B), \quad (4.1)$$

as can be verified by expressing the relevant probabilities in terms of p, q, r , and s .

Note that when A is certain, (4.1) reduces to the identity $P(B) = P_m(A \Rightarrow B)$. (The same is true of empirical implication, as will be evident from the following discussion.)

For *empirical* implication as well as for material, the near truth of A and of $A \Rightarrow B$ guarantees that of B, for a lower bound for $P(B)$ is clearly $P(A \Rightarrow B)P(A) = P(AB) \leq P(B)$. Indeed, $P(A \Rightarrow B) < P(B)$ when, and only when, $ps < qr$ -- i. e., when the determinant $ps-qr$ of the probability matrix is negative, or the events A and B are negatively correlated [BK, Sec. 5] -- since, as follows from (2.1),

$$P(B) = P(A \Rightarrow B) - (ps-qr)/(p+q). \quad (4.2)$$

Eq. (4.2) shows also that the right-hand inequality of (4.1) is valid for empirical implication iff $ps-qr > 0$ -- i. e., iff A and B are positively correlated.

Modus tollens

An analogous principle is modus tollens: if $A \Rightarrow B$ and B is false, then A is false. In this case, since $P(A)-P(B) = P(B')-P(A')$, we get the following analogue of (4.1):

$$P_m(A \Rightarrow B) + P(B') - 1 \leq P(A') \leq P_m(A \Rightarrow B). \quad (4.3)$$

Indeed, the left-hand inequality is valid also for empirical implication.

By (4.2), $P(B) = P(A \Rightarrow B)$ iff $ps = qr$, so it is not surprising that the latter condition is equivalent to the probabilistic independence of the properties A and B. Indeed, $ps-qr$ expresses the deviation from such independence, as is noted in [KS, Sec. 33.5]; see also [BK, Sec. 5].

Until now we have been considering only two propositions, A and B. Now we consider the case of three propositions (to which 2x2x2 contingency tables could be applied), and prove an evident general inequality, which is a generalization of some of the inequalities in the preceding displays.

Theorem 4.1. If the propositions X and Y together imply Z, then

$$P(X)+P(Y)-1 \leq P(XY) \leq P(Z). \quad (4.4)$$

Similarly, if X or Y implies Z, then

$$P(X)+P(Y)-1 \leq P(X \vee Y) \leq P(Z). \quad (4.5)$$

Proof. We prove only the first statement; the proof of the second is almost identical. Since $P(XY) = P(X)+P(Y)-P(X \vee Y)$ [F, p. 22], the left-hand inequality of (4.4) is now clear. Now let $A \equiv XY$ and $B \equiv Z$. Then $A \Rightarrow B$ iff $P(A \Rightarrow B) = P_m(A \Rightarrow B) = 1$ iff $q = P(AB') = 0$. If $q = 0$, as required by the hypothesis, then $P(B) = p+r \geq p+q = P(XY)$, as claimed.

By induction, this result can be extended to any number n (including 0) of conjuncts: If $X_1 X_2 \dots X_n \Rightarrow Z$, then $\sum P(X_i) - (n-1) \leq P(X_1 X_2 \dots X_n) \leq P(Z)$.

Transitivity

Now letting X, Y, and Z represent $A \Rightarrow B, B \Rightarrow C$ and $A \Rightarrow C$, respectively, in (4.4), we get the leftmost inequality of

$$P_m(A \Rightarrow B) + P_m(B \Rightarrow C) - 1 \leq P_m(A \Rightarrow C) \leq 1 \quad (4.6)$$

$$\leq P_m(A \Rightarrow B) + P_m(B \Rightarrow C).$$

(The rightmost inequality of (4.6) is equivalent to $P(AB') + P(BC') \leq 1$, which is valid since AB' and BC' are mutually exclusive.)

Hence if $P_m(A \Rightarrow B)$ and $P_m(B \Rightarrow C)$ are close to certainty, so is $P_m(A \Rightarrow C)$; in the extreme case of certainty, this gives the deterministic transitivity of material implication in formal logic: if $A \Rightarrow B$ and $B \Rightarrow C$, then $A \Rightarrow C$. To this extent, nearly certain material implication is transitive.

In contrast, as Minsky has already noted (ARPANET AIList Oct. 12, 1985), nearly certain *empirical* implication need not be transitive. It is possible that *no* A's are C's even if all A's are B's and most B's are C's; this is easily shown with a Venn diagram in which B is partitioned into A and C. This slight change from "all B's" to "most B's" completely destroys the classical Aristotelian syllogism known as "Barbara" [K2, p. 145]: All A's are B's and all B's are C's; therefore all A's are C's.

A special case is the following. Consider the probability matrix $P = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon r / (1 - \epsilon) & 0 \\ r & s \end{pmatrix}$, with $\epsilon r > 0$. Then $P(A \Rightarrow B) = 1$ and

$P(B \Rightarrow A) = 1 - \epsilon$, where ϵ can be arbitrarily small, yet $P(A \Rightarrow A) = 0$ -- the denial of transitivity is as great as possible.

Another application of Theorem 4.1 is to the rule of inference sometimes referred to [K2, p. 61] as "disjunctive syllogism": If A or B, and not-A, then B (cf. the definition (1.1) of material implication). Then $P(A \vee B) + P(A') - 1 \leq P(B)$, a result that could have been obtained directly from the probability matrix P of A and B.

Similarly, since $[A \Rightarrow C \text{ and } B \Rightarrow C] \Rightarrow [(A \vee B) \Rightarrow C]$, we conclude that $P_m(A \Rightarrow C) + P_m(B \Rightarrow C) - 1 \leq P_m((A \vee B) \Rightarrow C)$. (This also follows easily from the inequality $P(A \vee B) \leq P(A) + P(B)$.) Likewise, since $(A \Rightarrow B \text{ and } A \Rightarrow C) \Rightarrow (A \Rightarrow BC)$, we have $P_m(A \Rightarrow B) + P_m(A \Rightarrow C) - 1 \leq P_m(A \Rightarrow BC)$. Also valid, but not so immediate, are the empirical versions of these inequalities. But the empirical version is not true generally, as shown in the discussion on transitivity.

5. Summary

Frequencies of two joint properties A and B or their negations can conveniently be arranged in a 2x2 contingency table, or equivalently a 2x2 probability matrix

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} p & q \\ r & s \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} P(AB) & P(AB') \\ P(A'B) & P(A'B') \end{pmatrix}.$$

These permit easy calculation of the probability of a material implication such as $A \Rightarrow B$, which is $1 - q$. Generally the implication is uncertain, but when $q \equiv P(AB') = 0$, $A \Rightarrow B$ with probability one. Such a certain implication is equivalent to its contrapositive, $B' \Rightarrow A'$, both being equivalent to the impossibility of AB' (A and not-B), and to the certainty of $A \vee B$ (not-A or B).

We show by example that, on the contrary, in the inductive or "empirical" logic that governs most real-life decisions, $A \Rightarrow B$ is *not* equivalent to $B' \Rightarrow A'$: indeed, the two may have very different (conditional) probabilities. We have given sufficient conditions for the two to be *nearly* equal, as well as for the *near certainty* of the following implications:

- (a) If A is true and $A \Rightarrow B$, then B is true;
- (b) If B is false and $A \Rightarrow B$, then A is false.

However, the case of transitivity is different: the near certainty of $A \Rightarrow B$ and of $B \Rightarrow C$ need *not* imply that of $A \Rightarrow C$.

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